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Skinny Labeling at SCOTUS

Issue/Problem

The [Supreme Court of the United States's decision](#) to hear a patent dispute between Hikma and Amarin over Amarin's cardiovascular drug Vascepa addresses the issue of skinny labeling. Skinny labeling occurs under the [Hatch-Waxman Act](#) when a generic manufacturer seeks FDA approval via an Abbreviated New Drug Application (ANDA) for non-patented indications of an otherwise patented reference drug. For example, a generic may exclude indications covered by a method-of-use patent from their label, creating a "skinny label."

Description of the Problem

[Hikma obtained FDA approval](#) for a generic version of Vascepa limited to its original indication (severe hypertriglyceridemia), carving out Amarin's later-approved cardiovascular risk indication, which remained patent-protected. Despite this carve-out, Amarin sued Hikma alleging induced infringement, arguing that Hikma's public-facing communications encouraged physicians to prescribe the drug off-label for the patented cardiovascular use.

Results

The Trump administration supported Hikma's appeal [in an amicus curiae submission](#), saying that the Federal Circuit ruling in favour of Amarin represents a subversion of Congress's approach. At stake is whether compliance with FDA labeling requirements is sufficient to shield generics from patent liability, or whether communications can independently give rise to patent infringement liability. A finding in favour of Amarin could have a chilling effect on the entry of generic drugs into the market through the skinny label pathway.

Lessons Learned

A decision that limits inducement liability to label-based evidence would reinforce the FDA's position in approving uses and preserve regulatory predictability. A broader inducement standard would undermine FDA authority by effectively extending patent

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protection to non-patented indications. In the meantime, uncertainty surrounding the boundary of inducement discourages market entry and complicates R&D planning for generic manufacturers.